

Supplemental Table 1. Hypoglycemia symptom type by glucose range among individuals with intact and impaired awareness of hypoglycemia

	Intact awareness		Impaired awareness		Estimate 95%CI	Adjusted estimate 95%CI ¹
	N	%	n	%		
Glucose threshold at which autonomic symptoms first experienced					1.350, 1.657	1.341, 1.648
>70 mg/dL (1)	158	12.6	7	3.0		
63-70 mg/dL (2)	536	42.9	25	10.9		
54-62 mg/dL (3)	378	30.2	52	22.6		
45-53 mg/dL (4)	124	9.9	54	23.5		
<45 mg/dL (5)	31	2.5	55	23.9		
No autonomic symptoms (6)	23	1.8	37	16.1		
Glucose threshold at which neuroglycopenic symptoms first experienced					0.593, 0.940	0.593, 0.941
>70 mg/dL (1)	48	3.8	7	3.0		
63-70 mg/dL (2)	237	19.0	11	4.8		
54-62 mg/dL (3)	442	35.4	44	19.1		
45-53 mg/dL (4)	272	21.8	58	25.2		
<45 mg/dL (5)	161	12.9	89	38.7		
No neuroglycopenic symptoms (6)	90	7.2	21	9.1		
Glucose threshold at which other symptoms first experienced					0.032, 0.478	0.028, 0.472
>70 mg/dL (1)	41	3.3	11	4.8		
63-70 mg/dL (2)	121	9.7	12	5.2		
54-62 mg/dL (3)	179	14.3	14	6.1		
45-53 mg/dL (4)	160	12.8	33	14.3		
<45 mg/dL (5)	86	6.9	31	13.5		
No other symptoms (6)	663	53.0	129	56.1		

Number in parenthesis indicates the scoring scheme. Data analyzed with linear regression.

¹Adjusted for automated insulin delivery system use status. CI, confidence interval.

Supplemental Table 2. Ways in which hypoglycemia recognized during sleep among individuals with intact and impaired awareness of hypoglycemia

	Intact awareness		Impaired awareness		Estimate 95%CI	Adjusted estimate 95%CI ¹
	N	%	n	%		
Awoken by hypoglycemia symptoms					0.891, 1.214	0.887, 1.210
Always (0)	174	13.9	5	2.2		
Often (1)	343	27.4	18	7.8		
Sometimes (2)	407	32.6	51	22.2		
Rarely (3)	195	15.6	85	37.0		
Never (4)	131	10.5	71	30.9		
Awoken by someone else recognizing hypoglycemia					0.556, 0.836	0.551, 0.831
Never (0)	678	55.9	70	31.4		
Rarely (1)	298	24.6	55	24.7		
Sometimes (2)	175	14.4	54	24.2		
Often (3)	51	4.2	29	13.0		
Always (4)	10	0.8	15	6.7		
Not applicable	38	3.0	7	3.0		
Awoken by diabetes technology					-0.105, 0.191	-0.107, 0.190
Never (0)	37	3.0	3	1.3		
Rarely (1)	60	4.9	15	6.7		
Sometimes (2)	227	18.4	46	20.4		
Often (3)	368	29.8	51	22.7		
Always (4)	542	43.9	110	48.9		
Not applicable	16	1.3	5	2.2		

Number in parenthesis indicates the scoring scheme. Data analyzed with linear regression.

¹Adjusted for automated insulin delivery system use status. CI, confidence interval.

Supplemental Figure 1. Participant flow chart. CGM, continuous glucose monitoring